

STUDIES ON THE ENZYMES OF THE SEEDS OF *BUTEA FRONDOSA*. PART I. PROTEOLYTIC ENZYME.

BY N. R. CHATTERJEE, S. GHOSH AND R. N. CHOPRA.

The fresh seeds of *Butea frondosa* possess anthelmintic action, specially against ascaris. The seeds were found to contain proteolytic enzymes which hydrolyse peptones and casein, liquefy gelatin but have no action on egg-albumin or fibrin. They act best in a slightly alkaline medium and the optimum temperature is near about 40°. Hydrocyanic acid is found to have a definite activating influence. They behave like 'yeast trypsin' and appear to be a mixture of plant proteinase and polypeptidase.

The various parts of the common Indian plant *Butea frondosa*, like the bark, gum, leaves, flowers and seeds, have been used in the Indian indigenous medicine in various ailments from the very earliest times. The seeds are said to be aperient and anthelmintic, used with success in tape-worms and round-worms. Externally, the seeds are said to be useful in Dhobie's itch, ringworm, ulcers and fistula (*cf.* B. C. Gupta, "Ayurvedic Materia Medica", 1908, II, p. 54). As regards the therapeutic action, it is stated that the old worm-eaten seeds show little activity but freshly powdered seeds give fairly good results against ascaris (*cf.* Chopra, "Indigenous Drugs of India", 1933, p. 306).

A fair amount of chemical work has been carried out on all the constituents of the flowers, and some work is also reported on the gum. The seeds are reported to contain fatty oil, glucose, saccharose, starch, gum, phlobaphenes, proteins, etc. (Waber, *Pharm. Z. Ruszland*, 1896, 429; Heckel, "Graines grasses nouvelles des colonies francaises," Paris, 1902, 98). The most recent work on the seeds shows the presence of 18 % of fatty oil composed of glycerides of oleic, linolic, palmitic, lignoceric and other acids and the non-saponifiable matter has been found to contain sitosterol (Tummin Katti and Manjunath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 839).

The constituents so far identified in the seeds as well as those observed in the preliminary investigations carried out by us some years ago, do not seem to account for their definite anthelmintic action. The report that the fresh seeds show much stronger anthelmintic action than the old, worm-eaten ones, coupled with the fact that the proteolytic enzyme present in the

milky juice of *Ficus laurifolia* has been proved to be the anthelmintic principle of the juice (Robbins, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1930, 87, 251) led us to look for enzymes in the fresh seeds. The literature does not show any reference to the presence of any enzyme in the seeds of *Butea frondosa*. The present investigation confirmed the presence of both proteolytic and lipolytic enzymes in the seeds and an account of the proteolytic enzymes forms the subject of this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

For a preliminary examination, the following extracts were first made :

(1) 10% NaCl *Extract*.—Powdered seeds were soaked in the salt solution, thoroughly macerated, and the extract pressed out in a tincture press.

(2) 1% NaCl *Extract*.—Powdered seeds were treated with salt solution and the extract squeezed out.

(3) *Glycerine Extract*.—Powdered seeds were treated with 50% glycerine and the extract squeezed out in a tincture press.

(4) *Aqueous Extract* (enzyme cream) —5 G. of the powdered seeds were treated with distilled water (30 c.c.) and rubbed in a mortar for some time. The extract was squeezed out and the residue was again treated with water (30 c.c.) as before; the total extract measured 50 c.c., 10 c.c. being equivalent to 1 g. of seeds.

A preliminary examination with the above extracts showed that the aqueous extract (4) was best suited for the study of proteolytic activity and all the experiments shown below were carried out with this extract. In all the experiments the formol titration method was used and the results are expressed in terms of *N*/10-caustic soda. Toluene was used as preservative in all the experiments.

TABLE I.

Digestion of Witte's Peptone without Buffer.

Substrate = 15 c.c. peptone (5% soln. in 1% saline). p_H adjusted with standard HCl or NaOH. Enzyme cream = 15 c.c. Temperature = 37°.

p_H	4.7	5.1	6.2	6.4	8.2
Hydrolysis after 21 hrs. (in c.c. <i>N</i> /10-NaOH)	0.6	1.1	1.4	1.4	2.7

The above results show that the enzyme acts better on the alkaline side.

TABLE II.

Digestion of Witte's Peptone with Buffer.

Substrate=10 c.c. peptone (5% soln.). Phosphate buffer=5 c.c. Enzyme cream=10 c.c. Temperature=37°.

p_{H}	4.3	5.5	5.8	6.5	7.5	8.5
Hydrolysis after 48 hrs. (in c.c. <i>N/10-NaOH</i>)	3.2	4.0	3.9	4.4	5.3	4.5

The results show that maximum hydrolysis takes place when the medium is just alkaline.

TABLE III.

Digestion of Casein.

The casein solution was prepared by rubbing in a mortar 4g. of Merck's extra pure casein with 30 c. c. of *N/10-NaOH*, diluting with water (120 c.c.) and filtering through cotton wool. Substrate=10 c. c. casein solution. Phosphate buffer=5 c. c. Enzyme cream=10 c. c. Temperature=37°.

p_{H}	5.0	6.0	7.0	8.0
Hydrolysis after 18 hrs. (in c.c. <i>N/10-NaOH</i>)	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.7

The results show that casein is very little acted upon. It is in accordance with the previous observation that plant erepsins are not usually capable of hydrolysing casein like animal erepsins.

TABLE IV.

Digestion of Egg-albumin.

Substrate=15 c. c. egg-albumin (2% soln.). p_{H} adjusted with standard HCl or NaOH. Enzyme cream=10 c. c. Temperature=37°.

p_{H}	2.4	3.9	4.8	5.2	6.3	8.9
Hydrolysis after 21 hrs. (in c.c. <i>N/10-NaOH</i>)	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.9

There seems to be practically no action upon egg-albumin.

TABLE V.

Digestion of Gelatin.

2 C. c. of 5% gelatin containing 0.1% thymol were used as substrate. Different quantities of enzyme cream were added and the total volume made up to 4 c. c. by the addition of water; incubation for 24 hours at 37°.

Enzyme cream	Remarks.
2.0 c. c.	Liquefaction.
1.0	"
0.5	"
0.3	"
Nil	Solidify on cooling.

TABLE VI.

Digestion of Fibrin.

A small flock of Merck's fibrin from blood stained with Congo-red was used as substrate. 1 C. c. of different extractives of butea seeds was added in each experiment; incubation for 24 hours at 37°.

Extractives of :—	Remarks.
10% NaCl	Negative.
Glycerine with 0.1 c. c. of N/10-HCl	"
Glycerine with 0.1 c. c. of N/10-NaOH	"
Water with 0.1 c. c. of N/10-HCl	"
Water with 0.1 c. c. of N/10-NaOH	"

No digestion of fibrin was observed; it probably pointed to the ereptic nature of the enzyme.

TABLE VII.

Study of Optimum Reaction of the Medium with different Substrates.

Substrate=10 c. c. (3% soln.). Phosphate buffer=5 c. c. Enzyme cream=10 c. c. Incubation for 18 hours at 37°.

Hydrolysis in c. c. of <i>N/10-NaOH</i>				
p_H .	Peptone.	Casein.	Egg-albumin.	Gelatin.
5.0	0.8	0.2	Very slight	0.0
6.0	0.7	0.5	„	0.0
7.0	1.0	0.7	„	0.0
8.0	1.2	0.7	„	0.0

The results show that the enzyme acts best in the alkaline side, the optimum p_H lying in the neighbourhood of 8. It also shows that it acts best on peptone, there is some action on casein, while there is practically no action on egg-albumin and gelatin.

TABLE VIII.

Study of Optimum Temperature.

Substrate=10 c. c. Phosphate buffer=2 c. c. Enzyme cream=10 c. c. Temperature=37°. p_H of the medium=8.0. Incubation for 4 hours.

Hydrolysis in c. c. of <i>N/10-NaOH</i>					
Substrate.	at 30°.	at 40°.	at 50°.	at 60°.	at 70°.
Peptone	0.3	1.5	1.0	0.0	0.0
Casein	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.0	0.0

The results show that the optimum temperature is near about 40°.

TABLE IX.

Study of Activation of the Enzyme.

Substrate=10 c. c. Phosphate buffer=5 c. c. of p_H 7. Enzyme cream=
10 c. c. Activator=1 c. c. Incubation for 20 hours at 37°.

Activator.	Hydrolysis (N/10-NaOH)	
	Peptone.	Casein.
—	1.0 c. c.	0.6
2% HCN	1.8	1.6
H ₂ S (sat. soln.)	0.6	0.6

The results show that HCN activates both in peptone and casein hydrolysis but H₂S is without action.

TABLE X.

Study of the Activation of Enzyme without any Buffer.

Substrate=10 c. c. peptone. Enzyme cream=10 c. c. Activator=1 c. c.
Incubation for 24 hours at 37°.

Activator.	p_H .	Hydrolysis in N/10-NaOH.
—	5.9	1.4 c. c.
2% HCN	5.5	2.1
H ₂ S (Sat. soln.)	5.7	1.6

The results show that there is definite activation with HCN but practically none with H₂S. The phosphate buffer does not seem to have any retarding action as observed in the case of some plant protease (Basu and Nath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, *Ray Com. Vol.*, 1933, p. 107; *ibid.*, 1936, 13, 34).